

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.18831172

Assessment Of Nigerian University Accounting Curricula Alignment With The Accounting Industry Professional Needs: A Case Study Of Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the assessment of Nigerian university accounting curricula alignment with the accounting industry professional needs: a case study of Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam campus. The study developed two objectives such as to; Determine the effect of digital skills on industry professional needs in Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam campus; Ascertain the effect of curriculum relevance on industry professional needs in Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam campus. This research work will be anchored on the stakeholder theory. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. Data were generated from primary sources. The method for data collection was questionnaire which was administered randomly among the accountancy study of Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University. The population of the study was six hundred and forty-four (644) selected study, while the sample size was one hundred and twenty-four (124) using Borg and Gall formular. The hypotheses were tested using multiple regression analysis method at 0.05% level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that digital skills have significant effect on industry professional needs, Curriculum relevance have significant effect on industry professional needs. The study concluded that accounting curriculum at Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University demonstrates meaningful alignment with professional accounting needs, particularly in areas relating to digital competencies and curriculum relevance, the study recommended that. The university should further integrate advanced digital accounting tools into the curriculum. Courses should include practical training in accounting software (e.g., Sage, QuickBooks, SAP), data analytics, cloud accounting, blockchain fundamentals, and artificial intelligence applications in accounting. The accounting curriculum should be reviewed regularly in collaboration with industry experts, professional accounting bodies, and employers to ensure continuous relevance. This will help incorporate emerging trends, regulatory changes, and global best practices in accounting education.

Keywords: University accounting curricula, industry professional need, curriculum relevance, digital skills

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

The accounting profession plays a critical role in economic development through financial reporting, auditing, taxation, and management decision-making. Universities are primarily responsible for producing accounting graduates who possess the knowledge and skills required by the accounting industry and professional bodies (Carrera, 2010). However, rapid changes in business environments, globalization, and

technological advancement have significantly transformed the competencies required of professional accountants. As a result, accounting education must continually evolve to ensure that university curricula remain relevant to professional practice. In Nigeria, universities offer accounting programmes designed to provide students with theoretical knowledge and practical skills in financial accounting, auditing, taxation, and management accounting (Dyball et al., 2010),

The curriculum is often guided by regulatory agencies such as the National Universities Commission (NUC) and influenced by professional accounting bodies. Despite these efforts, concerns have been raised about the extent to which university accounting curricula meet the practical and technological requirements of the accounting profession. Studies indicate that accounting curricula significantly influence the employability and competence of graduates, and therefore should be designed in line with industry requirements (James, 2008; Lam et al., 2015). The accounting profession has undergone significant transformation due to developments such as International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS), digital accounting systems, and data-driven decision-making. The integration of global accounting standards such as IFRS into university curricula has become necessary to ensure that graduates can function effectively in modern accounting environments. However, insufficient integration of such professional standards and practical training has been identified as a major challenge in accounting education in Nigeria (Zhao et al., 2017).

Similarly, technological advancements have increased the need for accounting graduates to possess digital and analytical skills. The increasing use of accounting software and cloud-based financial systems has highlighted the importance of integrating digital accounting tools into university curricula. Nevertheless, many Nigerian tertiary institutions still rely on outdated teaching methods and lack adequate infrastructure and training to implement modern accounting practices (Apostolou et al., 2015). Furthermore, empirical studies have shown that gaps still exist between accounting education and professional requirements. For instance, research on Nigerian higher education institutions revealed limited integration of emerging areas such as sustainability accounting and social responsibility reporting, indicating that accounting curricula do not fully reflect global professional trends. These gaps may result in graduates who are theoretically knowledgeable but inadequately prepared for the practical demands of the accounting profession (Okolie, Igwe & Elom, 2019).

In addition, the need for closer collaboration between universities and employers has been emphasized in order to ensure that accounting programmes reflect current workplace realities. Curriculum developers are encouraged to obtain updated information from employers on required skills so that graduates can transition smoothly from academic training to professional practice (Adebisi & Gbegi, 2021). The Department of Accountancy at Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University was established to produce skilled and ethical accountants through a blend of theoretical instruction and practical training in areas such as financial reporting, taxation, auditing, and financial management. The programme emphasizes academic excellence and professional competence, with the objective of preparing graduates for employment in both private and public sector organizations. The university's accounting programme has also received accreditation, indicating compliance with national academic standards (ICAN, 2021).

However, accreditation alone does not guarantee that university curricula are fully aligned with the evolving needs of the accounting profession. Rapid changes in accounting technology, digital financial systems, and regulatory requirements have increased the need for continuous curriculum evaluation (Adeyemi, 2022). There is therefore a need to assess the extent to which the accounting curriculum at Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University reflects current industry expectations and professional standards. This study is motivated by the need to examine whether the accounting curriculum at Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University adequately prepares students for professional accounting practice. Specifically, the study seeks to evaluate the level of alignment between the university's accounting curriculum and the competencies required by employers and professional accounting bodies in Nigeria. The findings of the study are expected to provide useful insights for curriculum improvement and contribute to the enhancement of accounting education in Nigerian universities.

The accounting profession has undergone significant transformation in recent years due to globalization, technological advancement, and evolving financial reporting standards. Modern accountants are expected

to possess not only theoretical knowledge but also practical competencies in areas such as accounting software, data analytics, auditing techniques, and professional ethics. However, concerns have been raised about whether university accounting curricula in Nigeria adequately reflect the professional requirements of the accounting industry.

In many Nigerian universities, accounting education is still dominated by theoretical instruction with limited emphasis on practical skills and industry exposure. This situation has resulted in a noticeable gap between classroom learning and workplace expectations, leaving many graduates insufficiently prepared to meet professional accounting demands. The persistence of outdated course contents, inadequate integration of modern accounting technologies, and limited opportunities for internships and professional collaboration have further widened the gap between academic training and industry needs. Despite efforts by regulatory bodies and professional accounting organizations to improve accounting education standards, evidence suggests that many accounting curricula in Nigerian universities still do not fully align with emerging professional requirements such as sustainability reporting, digital accounting systems, and global accounting standards. Consequently, employers often face difficulties recruiting graduates who possess the required technical competence and practical experience needed in the accounting profession.

Specifically, at Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University in Anambra State, there is limited empirical evidence on the extent to which the accounting curriculum aligns with the needs of accounting professionals and industry stakeholders. Without such assessment, it is difficult to determine whether graduates from the institution possess the relevant skills and competencies required in modern accounting practice. Therefore, this study seeks to assess the extent to which the accounting curriculum of Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University aligns with the professional needs of the accounting industry. The study is necessary to identify gaps in the curriculum and provide recommendations for improving accounting education to enhance graduates' employability and professional competence.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The general objective of the study is an assessment of Nigerian university accounting curricula alignment with the accounting industry professional needs: a case study of Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam campus. The specific objectives of the study were as follow:

1. Determine the effect of digital skills on industry professional needs in Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam campus.
2. Ascertain the effect of curriculum relevance on industry professional needs in Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam campus.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Conceptual review

2.1.1. Curriculum

A curriculum refers to a structured plan that outlines the content, teaching methods, learning experiences, and assessment strategies designed to achieve specific educational outcomes (Oviawe & Eze, 2020). The concept of curriculum is fundamental in education because it defines the content, structure, and learning experiences provided to students in a formal educational setting. Curriculum serves as a guide for teaching and learning activities and determines the knowledge, skills, and attitudes students are expected to acquire within a specified period. Curriculum has been defined differently by various scholars and educational experts. According to Tyler (1949), curriculum refers to all planned learning experiences provided by an educational institution to achieve educational objectives. This definition emphasizes the structured nature of curriculum and its role in guiding educational outcomes. In a similar view, Taba (1962) defined curriculum as a plan for learning that includes objectives, content, learning experiences, and evaluation procedures. This definition highlights curriculum as a systematic process designed to facilitate effective learning.

Kerr (1968) defined curriculum as all the learning experiences that are planned and guided by the school, whether carried out individually or in groups, inside or outside the school. This definition broadens the concept of curriculum beyond classroom instruction to include practical and extracurricular learning

experiences. In another perspective, Wheeler (1976) described curriculum as the planned interaction of pupils with instructional content, materials, resources, and processes for evaluating the attainment of educational objectives. This definition emphasizes the interactive nature of curriculum and the importance of teaching methods and assessment.

Curriculum can also be seen as a structured body of knowledge organized into courses and programs of study. It includes subject content, instructional strategies, practical activities, and evaluation methods that help learners achieve desired competencies. In professional disciplines such as accounting, curriculum plays an important role in preparing students with both theoretical knowledge and practical skills required in the workplace. In the Nigerian context, the

National Board for Technical Education (NBTE) mandates curricula for polytechnics to emphasize technical competence and industry relevance. The polytechnic accounting curriculum is designed to produce middle-level manpower capable of applying accounting principles in public and private sector organizations. However, recent global and local evidence suggests that curricula are often outdated relative to emerging demands such as data analytics, sustainability reporting, and financial technology applications.

2.2 Theoretical Review

Stakeholder Theory

The stakeholder theory is a theory of organizational management and business ethics that addresses morals and values in managing an organization. It was originally detailed by Mitroff in his book 'Stakeholders of the Organizational Mind', published in 1983 in San Francisco (Mitroff 1983). The significance of stakeholder theory is that it recognizes that organizations are not controlled or affected purely by those that exercise ownership rights in the organization. As Freeman (2004) argued: the notion that shareholders govern the corporation is largely a fiction and typically, executives have the greatest power. In this sense, the conventional model of the corporation, in both legal and managerial forms, has failed to discipline self-serving managerial behavior.

The fundamental consequence of stakeholder theory for corporate governance is that it necessitates governance structures that promote alignment not just between agents and principals, but between agents, principals, and parties who have broader, but reasonable, interests in the organization. It is precisely because of this multifaceted approach to understanding corporate governance: that corporate governance should be responsive to multiple, competing interests, which provide intellectual rigor to a stakeholder framework. According to Clarkson (1995), the main criticism of stakeholder theory is focusing on identifying the problem of who constitutes genuine stakeholders. Another argument is that meeting stakeholders' interests also leads to corruption, as it offers agents the opportunity to divert the wealth away from shareholders to others. Stakeholder theory is highly relevant to the assessment of accounting curricular alignment with accounting industry professional needs because it emphasizes the importance of considering the interests and expectations of all groups affected by educational programs. Stakeholders are individuals or groups who can influence or are influenced by the achievement of an organization's objectives, including employers, students, lecturers, professional bodies, and government agencies.

2.3 Empirical Review

Fehintola, Umaigba and Lasisi, (2026) examined the relevance, effectiveness, and industrial needs of the accounting curriculum in Nigerian polytechnics. The research was motivated by growing concerns that accounting graduates, while theoretically sound, often lack the practical, digital, and professional skills required by industry. Using a descriptive survey design, data were collected from 356 respondents, comprising lecturers, final year students, recent graduates, and employers across selected polytechnics in Nigeria. A structured questionnaire was validated through expert review and pilot testing, achieving reliability coefficients above 0.70. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation, and regression techniques. Findings revealed that the accounting curriculum, though relevant in providing core financial reporting and taxation knowledge, is outdated in emerging areas such as data analytics, forensic accounting, ICT-based accounting tools, and sustainability reporting. Curriculum effectiveness was found to be moderate, with teaching largely delivered through traditional lecture methods, lacking modern pedagogical practices such as case studies, simulations, and ICT-based learning. Industry

linkages, particularly the Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES), were poorly implemented and inconsistently supervised, reducing their impact on employability. Regression results showed that curriculum effectiveness had the strongest influence on employability, followed by curriculum relevance and industry linkages, jointly explaining 58% of the variance in graduate employability outcomes.

Jindarat, et al. (2025) investigated from the viewpoint of employers, how the caliber of accounting education impacts the job performance of accounting graduates in Sri Lanka. A total of five criteria were employed to assess the quality of accounting education: communication skills, ethical standards, digital competencies, foundational accounting knowledge, and adaptability. The research involved administering a questionnaire to finance managers linked to firms on the Colombo Stock Exchange, with the findings interpreted via multiple regression analysis. The findings revealed that while foundational accounting knowledge did not exhibit a significant effect on performance, digital competencies, ethical standards, communication skills, and adaptability did indeed have a notable impact. Findings show that to advance the readiness of graduates for labor opportunities in Sri Lanka, accounting programs should be framed around the enhancement of practical know-how and the establishment of synergies between industry players and academic institutions.

Ramadhan, et al. (2024) investigated the alignment between Iraqi university accounting courses and industry demands to enhance the standard and relevance of accounting education. The primary research method was a questionnaire, aiming to understand how well accounting courses at Iraqi institutions meet market requirements. The study's methodology comprised two parts: examining the current accounting curriculum and conducting a follow-up survey using diverse sources and analytical techniques. A total of 350 surveys were distributed to academics and employers, yielding 87 responses from academic staff and 102 valid responses from employers. The study analyzed the latest accounting curriculum, demographic data, relevance ratings for courses, and assessments of essential work skills using SPSS software. Results revealed diverse demographics, with significant responses from academics (58%) and employers (51%). Findings indicate both convergence and divergence in the perceived importance of specific accounting courses, suggesting gaps between theoretical concepts and practical applications. The report underscores the need to align Iraq's accounting curriculum with business needs.

Zalida, Anda and Renda, (2024) evaluated and compare the competencies required for accounting professionals, specifically focusing on intellectual, technical, organizational, interpersonal, and personal competencies, as well as the effectiveness of current learning methods used in universities. By identifying the gaps between the competencies required in the industry and the learning methods applied by higher education institutions (HEIs), the study intends to highlight areas for improvement to better prepare accounting students for the professional world. A quantitative descriptive method was used, involving a survey distributed via Google Forms to practitioners in accounting, finance, and auditing. The analysis compares competencies taught in university courses with those demanded by the industry. Data from syllabus reviews, practitioners' feedback, and a literature review of relevant frameworks were utilized to assess the alignment of educational practices with industry needs. The study found that while HEIs effectively cover intellectual and technical competencies, there is a gap in organizational and management skills. Additionally, the methods used by universities, particularly lectures and group discussions, do not fully align with industry expectations. Practitioners emphasize the need for more case-based and project-based learning to improve practical skills, with leadership and time-management competencies identified as areas needing improvement. The research is limited by the sample size and the reliance on survey data from practitioners in specific fields. The findings may not be generalizable to all accounting education systems. Future research could explore the impact of specific teaching methods on student competencies and expand the sample to include more diverse industries.

Omotehinse, (2023) reviewed the recent development in Accounting education and Accounting practice. The qualitative and library research was employed for the study. The study found that it has been found that the current accounting courses offered by several Nigerian universities are insufficient in meeting the labor market needs. Also found further that there is a significant disparity exists between employers and educators regarding the importance of graduate skills. It is therefore concluded that there should be a

stronger relationship and collaboration among accounting practitioners, policymakers, and academic researchers are vital for shaping the future of accounting work and determining the type of accounting that will be practiced and studied. The study recommended that it is the responsibility of universities to establish a robust educational foundation for professional accounting training and it is imperative to reintroduce compulsory internship programs before graduation, similar to the practices in other professions like law and medicine.

Tufuor and Servoh, (2023) compared the accounting curricula of selected universities in Africa, America, Asia, and Europe, guided by International Education Standards (IES) 2, 3, 4, and 5. Fourteen universities from different continents were conveniently selected, and a descriptive content analysis was conducted to analyse the undergraduate accounting program contents. The findings reveal that the accounting education in selected African universities aligns with IES 2, 3, 4 and other universities, countering claims of inferiority. However, the universities' curricula in Africa lack practical job-related competencies (IES 5) due to limited opportunities for experiential learning. Disparities exist in the emphasis on IES competencies, potentially leading to imbalanced development among graduates. African universities prioritise employment-oriented education, while those in America, Asia, and Europe emphasise professional progression.

METHODOLOGY

3.1. Research Design

The research design used in this study was survey design; the researcher will use it to seek clarifications and convenience on the part of the respondent given schedules.

3.2 Primary Data

Data was collected through the administration of questionnaire which was instruments of the survey method research.

3.3. Population of the Study

The population for the study comprised the student of accounting in Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University. The researcher choose 300 level and 400l students for this study, the reason is because they have pass through some of the curriculum and be able to differentiate the core and relevance of those curriculum. The total population was six hundred and forty-four (644)

3.4 Sample size determination

Given the nature of this study, it was difficult to cover the entire population of (644), so a fair representative sample of the population therefore was imperative. Accordingly, the sample size for the study was determined by using the Borg & Gall (1973) guidelines for calculating sample size as follows

$$n = (1.960)^2 (0.05) [644]$$

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$$n = (3.8461) (32.2)$$

$$123.8444 \quad \Longrightarrow \quad 124$$

n = 124 stand for the sample size

3.5 Instrument for data Collection.

The instrument for the data collection that was utilized for this study is structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was structured in the line with variables of the study already stated in the hypothesis. A questionnaire will consist of different kinds of information and questions.

3.6 Method of data analysis

The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Analyses were carried out with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) and Regression Analysis.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Table 4.1: Model Summary

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.786 ^a	.618	.615	.82647	.618	258.315	2	122	.000	1.540

- a. Predictors: (Constant), DGS, CCR
- b. Dependent Variable: IPN

Table 4.1 above shows that R² which measures the strength of the effect of independent variable on the dependent variable has the value of 61%. which implies that 61% of the variation in industry professional needs is explained by variations in digital skill and curriculum relevance. This was supported by adjusted R² of 0.615%. In order to check for autocorrelation in the model, Durbin-Watson statistics was employed. Durbin-Watson statistics of 1.540 in table above showed that the variables in the model are not auto correlated and that the model is reliable for predications

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	352.889	2	176.444	258.315	.000^b
	Residual	218.579	320	.683		
	Total	571.467	322			

- a. Dependent Variable: IPN
- b. Predictors: (Constant), DGS, CCR

The f-statistics value of 18.315 in table above with f-statistics probability of 0.000 shows that the independent variables has significant effect on dependent variables such as digital skill and curriculum relevance can collectively explain the variations in industry professional needs.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	.113	.172		6.461	.000	.774	1.451
	DGS	.774	.034	.785	2.656	.001	.707	.841
	CCR	.008	.035	.008	2.238	.004	.076	.060

- a. Dependent Variable: IPN

A’p priori Criteria: This is determined by the existing accounting theories; it also indicates the signs and magnitude of the accounting parameter under review. In table above, we found out that digital skills has a positive sign given its value as .774, this implies that a unit increase in digital skills increases the industry professional needs by 77%, this conform to the a’ priori expectation. Curriculum relevance has a positive sign given its value as .008; this implies that a unit increase in Curriculum relevance increases the industry professional needs by 8%, this conform to a’ priori expectation.

However, digital skill variables have regression t-value of 2.656 with a probability value of 0.001. This implies that digital skill has a positive and significant effect on industry professional needs. Curriculum relevance has a regression t-test of 2.238 with a probability value of 0.004, implying that Curriculum relevance variable have positive and significant effect on industry professional needs

4.2 Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis one

H₀₁: Digital skills have no significant effect on industry professional needs in Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam campus.

Interpretation:

Drawing inference from our regression result on **Coefficients^a** table above, the findings showed that the t-value of Digital skills (DGS) is 2.656 which is greater than 2, with P=0.001 which is less than P< 0.05

level of significance and at 95% level of confidence intervals: (lower bound= 0.707, upper bound=0.841) which means zero lies within the confidence interval with which the researcher worked. Based on the findings from the result, we reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and accept the alternative hypothesis (H_1) which stated that Digital skills have significant effect on industry professional needs in Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam campus

Hypothesis Two

Ho2: Curriculum relevance have no significant effect on industry professional needs in Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam campus

Interpretation:

Drawing inference from our regression result in table 4.4.5 above, the findings showed that the t-value of Curriculum relevance (CCR) is 2.238 which is greater than 2, with $P=0.004$ which is less than $P < 0.05$ level of significance and at 95% level of confidence intervals: (lower bound= 0.076, upper bound=0.060) which means zero lies within the confidence interval with which the researcher worked. Based on the findings from the result, we reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and accept the alternative hypothesis (H_1) which stated that Curriculum relevance have significant effect on industry professional needs in Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam campus

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Conclusion

This study assessed the alignment between Nigerian university accounting curricula and the professional needs of the accounting industry, with specific reference to Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University. The objective was to determine whether the existing accounting curriculum adequately equips graduates with the competencies required by modern accounting professionals and employers.

The findings revealed that digital skills have a significant and positive effect on industry professional needs. This indicates that proficiency in accounting software, data analytics tools, enterprise resource planning (ERP) systems, and emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence and cloud accounting significantly enhances graduates' relevance in today's technology-driven accounting environment. The result underscores the growing demand for digitally competent accountants who can function effectively in automated and data-intensive workplaces.

Furthermore, the study established that curriculum relevance has a significant and positive effect on industry professional needs. This suggests that when accounting curricula are structured to reflect current professional standards, regulatory requirements, and industry practices, graduates are better prepared to meet employer expectations. A well-aligned curriculum ensures that theoretical knowledge is complemented with practical exposure, case studies, internship opportunities, and contemporary accounting practices.

Overall, the study concludes that the accounting curriculum at Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University demonstrates meaningful alignment with professional accounting needs, particularly in areas relating to digital competencies and curriculum relevance. However, continuous review and adaptation remain necessary to keep pace with rapid technological advancements and evolving professional standards within the accounting profession.

5.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study on the assessment of Nigerian university accounting curricular alignment with professional accounting needs at Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, the following recommendations are made:

i. The university should further integrate advanced digital accounting tools into the curriculum. Courses should include practical training in accounting software (e.g., Sage, QuickBooks, SAP), data analytics, cloud accounting, blockchain fundamentals, and artificial intelligence applications in accounting. This will enhance students' technological competence and align them with current industry expectations.

ii. The accounting curriculum should be reviewed regularly in collaboration with industry experts, professional accounting bodies, and employers to ensure continuous relevance. This will help incorporate emerging trends, regulatory changes, and global best practices in accounting education.

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